

Comparison of Prophylactic Intravenous Butorphanol And Intravenous Clonidine For Preventing Intraoperative Shivering After Neuraxial Anesthesia

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Abstract

Background: Use of Butorphanol and Clonidine for treatment of intraoperative shivering shows varying results in literature. Hence this study was conducted to compare the efficacy of Butorphanol and Clonidine for treatment of intraoperative shivering.

Methods: This comparative study was conducted among 80 elective surgery cases undergoing spinal anesthesia in Trichy SRM Medical College hospital and Research Centre. Patients in age groups of 18-60 years from both gender belongs to ASA class I and II were included. Pregnant females and cases allergic to study drugs were excluded. Among the 80 cases forty cases were included in Butorphanol group (group B) and rest forty cases were included in Clonidine group (group C). Group B received 1 mg of intravenous Butorphanol and Group C received 150 mcg of intravenous clonidine 5 minutes before spinal anesthesia as a prophylactic dose. Data was analysed using SPSS 19.

Results: In this study, in both group B and group C were similar in terms of age, gender and ASA class. Notably, there were two cases and eight cases in group B and group C, respectively. On assessing the association between presences of shivering between groups there was a statistically significant association noted. In group B, there were 38 cases with grade 0 shivering and one case each in grade 1 and grade 2. Similarly, there were 32 cases in grade 0, 4 cases in grade 1, 2 cases in grade 2 and one case each in grade 3 and grade 4. On assessing the adverse effects between groups, PONV, bradycardia and hypotension were not significantly associated.

Conclusion: We infer that butorphanol is comparatively better in terms of reducing shivering compared to Clonidine without altering hemodynamic parameters. Hence we recommend prophylactic intravenous butorphanol than intravenous clonidine for preventing intraoperative shivering after neuraxial anesthesia.

Key words: Butorphanol, Clonidine, Shivering, Intraoperative

INTRODUCTION

Shivering is a typical thermoregulatory reaction to hypothermia, wherein the body produces extra heat¹. One side effect of spinal anesthesia is shivering. It obstructs the patient's blood pressure, oxygen saturation, and ECG monitoring. The loss of thermoregulatory regulation during spinal anesthesia is the cause of shivering in about 56.7% is the reported occurrence^{2,3}. Shivering and a drop in core body temperature are caused by the cold environment of the operating room, the infusion of cold fluids, and the disruption of the body's temperature regulation mechanism when under anesthesia^{1,4}.

One consequence of regional anesthesia is the disruption of autonomic thermoregulation. Additionally, it inhibits peripheral vasoconstriction, and the intraoperative drop in core body temperature is caused by these two causes. The degree of reduction in the thresholds for shivering and vasoconstriction is related to the number of blocked segments, and it is 0.6 degrees Celsius below the level of block⁵⁻⁷. Patients experiencing spinal anesthesia may find it quite upsetting if they shiver. Severe shivering can increase oxygen demand by 200–500%, while mild shivering raises oxygen requirements to a level comparable to that of light exercise. Shivering can impair patient monitoring and raise intracranial and intraocular pressure.⁴ Shivering is harmful to people with low cardio-respiratory reserves and can also rarely cause arterial hypoxemia⁸. Given the information above, it is imperative to prevent shivering in the first place and to act quickly to control it when it does occur. There are a number of ways to manage shivering while under regional anesthesia. Non pharmacological techniques to manage shivering necessitate the use of devices such as fluid warmers and blanket warmers. These tools are pricey, and because they are not always available, they cannot be used in every situation. One pharmacological approach to managing shivering is to take medication. Although other medications have been tried, including ondansetron, clonidine, doxapram, pethidine, ketanserine, and nefopam, the best antishivering medication is still up for dispute.

Via the κ (Kappa) and μ (mu) receptors, butorphanol tartrate is a centrally acting opioid analgesic with strong anti-shivering effects⁹. Alpha-2 adrenoreceptor agonist clonidine has sedative, analgesic, antihypertensive, and antishivering qualities. By reducing the release of nor-adrenaline from the hypothalamic axonal terminals, clonidine has the antishivering action¹⁰.

With these in view this study was conducted to compare the efficacy of Butorphanol and Clonidine for treatment of intraoperative shivering.

METHODS

This comparative study was conducted among 80 elective surgery cases undergoing spinal anesthesia in Trichy SRM Medical College hospital and Research Centre. Patients in age groups of 18-60 years from both gender belongs to ASA class I and II were included. Pregnant females and cases allergic to study drugs were excluded. Earlier study by Nandhakumar et al had shown that shivering was controlled by 83% in Butorphanol group and 53% in clonidine group. Assuming similar observations was made in the present study; adequate sample size for 80% power at 5% level of significance is 40 per group. Among the 80 cases forty cases were included in Butorphanol group (group B) and rest forty cases were included in Clonidine group (group C). Group B received 1 mg of intravenous Butorphanol and Group C received 150 mcg of intravenous clonidine 5 minutes before spinal anesthesia as a prophylactic dose.

All enrolled patients are admitted prior to day of operation. After arrival in the operation theatre, monitoring for heart rate, electrocardiogram, pulse-oximetry, noninvasive arterial blood pressure and axillary temperature are noted. Under all aseptic precautions, pt in Lateral position, subarachnoid block was given at L2-L3 or L3-L4 intervertebral space with 3.5 ml of 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine (17.5 mg). The sensory and motor block characteristics are assessed till required surgical anaesthesia is achieved. The hemodynamic parameters of systolic & diastolic blood pressure, heart rate, ECG and pulse oximetry are monitored at 5 minute intervals till end of surgery. Intraoperatively shivering was recorded at 5-minute interval up to 60 minutes of surgery, using a scale validated by Wrench. Grade 0: No shivering, Grade 1: Piloerection but no visible muscular activity, Grade 2: Visible muscular activity confined to one muscle group, Grade 3: Visible muscular activity in more than one muscle group but not generalized, Grade 4: Gross muscular activity (Shivering) involving the whole body. The prophylaxis for shivering was regarded as ineffective if the patient exhibits grade-3 shivering any time during the study. Patients, who developed grade 3 or more of shivering were treated with tramadol (50 mg) and ondansetron (4 mg) intravenously. Data was analysed using SPSS 19. Chi square test was used to test the hypothesis. P value of < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

In this study, both group B and group C were similar in terms of age, gender and ASA class with no statistical significant association.

Table 1: Clinical Profile of study participants

Variables	Group B	Group C	p value
Age group			
18-30 years	6	9	0.4327
31-40 years	12	10	
41-50 years	13	12	
51-60 years	9	9	
Total	40	40	
Gender			
Male	23	21	0.7532
Female	17	19	
Total	40	40	
ASA class			
Class II	16	15	0.8642
Class II	24	25	
Total	40	40	

Notably, there were two cases and eight cases in group B and group C, respectively. On assessing the association between presences of shivering between groups there was a statistically significant association noted.

Table 2: Proportion of shivering with Intra-operative Shivering

Introp Shivering	Group B	Group C	p value
Present	2	8	0.0425*
Absent	38	32	
Total	40	40	

*Significant

In group B, there were 38 cases with grade 0 shivering and one case each in grade 1 and grade 2. Similarly, there were 32 cases in grade 0, 4 cases in grade 1, 2 cases in grade 2 and one case each in grade 3 and grade 4.

Table 3: Grading of shivering in each group

Grading of Shivering	Group B	Group C
Grade 0	38	32
Grade 1	1	4
Grade 2	1	2
Grade 3	0	1
Grade 4	0	1
Total	40	40

On assessing the adverse effects between groups, PONV, bradycardia and hypotension were not significantly associated.

Table 4: Proportion of different adverse effects in each group

Adverse effects	Group B	Group C	p value
PONV			
Present	1	4	0.1658
Absent	39	36	
Bradycardia			
Present	1	0	0.3141
Absent	39	40	
Hypotension			
Present	1	0	0.3141
Absent	39	40	

DISCUSSION

The effectiveness of granisetron and butorphanol in reducing shivering in patients undergoing spinal anesthesia was assessed by Prathibha SD et al¹¹. The timing of beginning of action was statistically significant because butorphanol started to work in three to five minutes, whereas

granisteron required five to seven minutes to stop shivering. After five, ten, and thirty minutes, there was a statistically significant difference in the heart rates of the two groups. Additionally, a statistical analysis revealed that the difference in MAP between the two groups at 10 and 30 minutes was significant. They asserted that compared to Granisetron, butorphanol had a noticeably higher frequency of tachycardia, hypotension, and vomiting. Butorphanol had a milder sedative effect and a quicker onset of action. Granisetron therefore controls shivering better than butarphanol. The effectiveness of butorphanol and clonidine in reducing shivering in patients having spinal anesthesia was examined by Sajidhusain B et al¹². 60 patients were randomly assigned to groups B (butorphanol) and C (clonidine) in the current investigation. The two groups' baseline axillary temperature, age, weight, BMI, gender, ASA grade, length of operation, and other characteristics were similar and did not show any statistically significant differences. When comparing the butorphanol group to the clonidine group, a statistically significant difference was observed in the earlier onset and longer duration of both sensory and motor block. The current investigation found a statistically significant difference in the incidence of shivering between the clonidine and butorphanol groups. Hypotension, nausea, and vomiting were more common side effects in the clonidine group than in the butorphanol group, and the difference was statistically noteworthy. Three patients in each group had bradycardia. They stated that intravenous butorphanol had an early onset and a longer duration of sensory/motor block and is safe and effective in preventing shivering.

According to Singh S et al¹³, butorphanol and tramadol are more effective than clonidine at reducing shivering. Eighty-three percent of the patients experienced a significant reduction in rigors after receiving butorphanol, tramadol, and clonidine, respectively. When compared to butorphanol and tramadol, the administration of clonidine produced a longer duration of activity. They came to the conclusion that butorphanol treatment was more effective than tramadol at controlling shivering, with fewer recurrences. Butorphanol and tramadol, on the other hand, demonstrated greater effectiveness when compared to clonidine, along with the advantage of an early commencement of action. When under spinal anesthesia, the effects of butorphanol and dexmedetomidine on shivering were assessed and compared by Savarn S et al¹⁴. According to their findings, following medication administration, 4 out of 35 patients in group B and 34 out of 35 patients showed a decline in HR < 20% of baseline. In comparison to group B, group D experienced a considerably higher frequency of heart rate decreases (97.1% vs. 11.4%). For the

patients in group B, the average length of surgery was 2.07 hours. For the patients in group D, the average length of surgery was 2.37 hours. For both groups, the length of the procedure stayed the same. Group B experienced a considerably higher frequency of recurrences of shivering than group D; in the event of a recurrence, intravenous tramadol 0.5 mg/kg was administered as a rescue medication. A substantially greater proportion of patients in group B had sedation score 3 whereas in group D a significantly bigger proportion of subjects had sedation score 4. They claimed that management of shivering is better with dexmedetomidine than butorphanol. By far, dexmedetomidine has a lower rate of recurrence than butorphanol. When compared to butorphanol, dexmedetomidine has a much higher incidence of hemodynamic abnormalities. Compared to butorphanol, they found that Dexmedetomidine, at a dose of 0.5 µg/kg, efficiently reduces intraoperative shivering in patients receiving subarachnoid blockade.

The relative effectiveness of butorphanol and tramadol given intravenously in preventing shivering during the intraoperative phase after spinal anesthesia was assessed by Chandan RK et al¹⁵. During the study period, 76 individuals had shivering after spinal anesthesia. Of these patients, 38 underwent intravenous tramadol treatment while the remaining 38 underwent intravenous butorphanol treatment. The mean temperature at which individuals developed shivering was 36.22°C and the mean time for shivering to occur after spinal anesthesia was 28.82 min. Shivering was controlled by butorphanol in an average of 190.53 seconds, and by tramadol in an average of 205.47 seconds. For the two groups, there was no statistically significant variance in the amount of time needed to control shivering. While tramadol had no failures and no recurrence of shivering, butorphanol failed to control shivering in two patients and caused recurrences in seven patients. They came to the conclusion that, after spinal anesthesia, intravenous tramadol 1 mg/kg was more efficient than butorphanol 20 µg/kg in suppressing shivering. Furthermore, compared to patients treated with intravenous butorphanol, those receiving tramadol experienced a higher incidence of nausea and vomiting.

Two medications, butorphanol and clonidine, were administered intravenously to suppress shivering while under spinal anesthesia. Bhosale JP et al¹⁶. compared their efficacy in this regard. Regarding the demographic profile, length of surgery, and mean time until shivering started, the research groups were similar. Taking Clonidine took longer than taking Butorphanol to control shivering. With clonidine, the incidence of recurrence was substantially higher than

with butorphanol. Comparing Clonidine to Butorphanol, the percentage of side effects such as bradycardia and hypotension was much higher. Between the two groups, the incidence of sedation did not differ statistically significantly. They asserted that butorphanol is superior to clonidine in terms of controlling shivering that happens during spinal anesthesia. Butorphanol's benefits include quicker onset of action, a decreased risk of shivering recurrence, and a decreased risk of adverse effects such as bradycardia and hypotension. Fentanyl and butorphanol were contrasted by Manne VSSK et al¹⁷ to treat postoperative shivering during spinal anesthesia. Fentanyl provides faster and more efficient shiver relief than butorphanol. When shivering first appears, there is a notable drop in core body temperature along with an increase in pulse rate, MAP, RR, and decreased oxygen saturation. With butorphanol and fentanyl, sedation, nausea, vomiting, and recurrent shivering are more common. They came to the conclusion that fentanyl works faster and more efficiently than butorphanol to treat perioperative shivering.

After spinal anesthesia, Attal P et al¹⁸ assessed the relative effectiveness of intravenously given tramadol and clonidine for controlling intraoperative shivering. At 1 minute, 2 minute, 3 minute, and 5 minute intervals, the tramadol group's reaction rate was significantly higher than the clonidine group's, and at 15 minutes, it was comparable for both groups. In the clonidine group, the average time taken for the shivering to stop was 5.76 minutes, compared to 3.16 minutes in the tramadol group. In the clonidine group, there were more patients with incomplete response and recurrence. Patients in the clonidine group experienced manageable side effects such as bradycardia, hypotension, drowsiness, and dry mouth, while those in the tramadol group experienced nausea and vomiting. According to their claims, Tramadol is superior to clonidine in terms of controlling intraoperative shivering under spinal anesthesia because of its quicker onset, greater response rate, less recurrence, less sedation, and less changes to hemodynamics. Under spinal anesthesia, Bansal P et al¹⁹ assessed the effectiveness of tramadol, butorphanol, and clonidine in controlling shivering and compared their adverse effects. Clonidine was less successful than butorphanol and tramadol in reducing shivering. In 83%, 73%, and 53% of cases, butorphanol, tramadol, and clonidine, respectively, totally controlled rigors; in 16%, 26%, and 46% of cases, they only partially suppressed rigors. Clonidine required a much longer time to end rigors than butorphanol and tramadol did. They found that although both were better than clonidine for this goal with an early beginning of action, butorphanol had an advantage over

tramadol in suppressing shivering with a decreased likelihood of recurrence. They found that both of these opioids are more effective at controlling rigors than α -2 agonists.

Compared to tramadol, Wan JX et al²⁰ found that butorphanol causes more drowsiness, a shorter time to stop shivering, and a higher rate of shivering cessation within 1 minute after the study medicines are administered. They stated that compared to tramadol, butorphanol has a faster start time and a greater rate of shivering cessation within 1 minute of the study medicines being provided for the treatment of shivering following spinal anesthesia. For this reason, butorphanol works better than tramadol to alleviate shivering following spinal anesthesia. The effectiveness and safety of intravenous tramadol and clonidine for the treatment of shivering during spinal anesthesia were compared by Aravind A et al²¹. Both groups experienced control over shivering, however the Tramadol group experienced early control and late recurrence, whereas the Clonidine group experienced delayed control and early recurrence. In both groups, hemodynamic parameters were kept within 15% of the initial values. Both groups experienced nausea and vomiting as complications, but there was no discernible difference. It was discovered that clonidine sedated people more than tramadol. They came to the conclusion that, in order to control postspinal shivering, 1 mg/kg of intravenous tramadol is a great substitute for 1 μ g/kg of intravenous clonidine because it offers early control, delayed recurrence of shivering, and minimum side effects.

According to Alijanpour E²², the Clonidine group experienced shivering at a considerably lower rate than the other groups. The group that received clonidine had analgesia for a noticeably longer period of time than the control group. The study found no statistically significant differences in side effects between the groups. The study's findings demonstrated that clonidine taken orally can help reduce shivering and other adverse effects following spinal anesthesia. The relative effectiveness of prophylactic intravenous clonidine and tramadol for the management of intraoperative shivering after spinal anesthesia was assessed by Guha S et al²³. Between the two groups, there was no significant difference in the incidence of shivering. When the rescue medication was given to the patients who shivered, the axillary temperatures in Group C dramatically decreased from the baseline and stayed there for an additional 60 minutes. While there was a comparable drop in axillary temperature in Group T among shivering patients, the difference was not statistically significant. The difference in temperature drop between the two

groups of patients who shivered was not statistically significant. While nausea was considerably more common in patients taking tramadol, side symptoms such hypotension, bradycardia, and drowsiness were significantly more common in the clonidine group. Using both clonidine and tramadol prophylactically under spinal anesthesia effectively manages shivering. Tramadol, on the other hand, is superior due to its increased reaction rate, decreased sedation, and lessened hemodynamic changes.

The usefulness of oral clonidine in preventing post-subarachnoid block shivering in patients following elective urological surgery was investigated by Dhorigol MG et al²⁴. In both groups, the core temperature remained constant. There were statistically significant variations in the incidence of post-subarachnoid block shivering between clonidine 150 µg and placebo, with shivering being rated as none, mild, moderate, and severe. The hemodynamics of both groups did not significantly change. They stated that individuals undergoing elective urological surgery can avoid post-subarachnoid block shivering by taking 150 µg of clonidine orally as a premedication. The effectiveness of butorphenol and ondosteron in reducing postoperative shivering was evaluated by Rai S et al²⁵. In general anesthesia groups I, II, and III, postoperative shivering was noted in 15.5%, 22.2%, and 60% of cases, respectively. All three groups experienced similar reductions in heart rate, systolic and diastolic blood pressure, and core and skin temperature throughout anesthesia and recovery. PAS occurred in groups IV, V, and VI at rates of 10%, 13.3%, and 43.3%, respectively, under spinal anesthesia. There is a comparable decrease in core temperature across all three spinal anesthesia groups. However, throughout the postoperative recovery period, there was a substantial rise in HR and MAP in the control saline group. Not a single problem was observed in the six groups.

CONCLUSION

We infer that butorphenol is comparatively better in terms of reducing shivering compared to Clonidine without altering hemodynamic parameters. Hence we recommend prophylactic intravenous butorphanol than intravenous clonidine for preventing intraoperative shivering after neuraxial anesthesia.

Declarations

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Conflict of interest: None declared

Ethical approval: This study was registered with Institutional Human Ethical Committee.

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